

A STUDY OF ADJUSTMENT AMONG B. ED TEACHER TRAINEES IN WEST GODAVARI DISTRICT OF ANDHRA PRADESH

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Abstract

Student teachers are the future goal setters. It is very important to monitoring how they are learning and acquiring the practical and theoretical knowledge for the future development and growth in the career profession. This study focus on adjustment of B. Ed teacher trainees. Normative survey method was adopted and stratified random sampling was chosen for study. 300 students participated in this study were obtained from 13 B. Ed Colleges at West Godavari district. The main objectives were 1.To assess the level of adjustment among teacher trainees 2. To study the influence of the adjustment among teacher trainees with certain variables like gender, locality, religion, marital status and academic stream. The study revealed that moderate level of academic stress of teacher trainees. Gender, locality is significantly influenced their academic stress. Religion, marital status and academic stream have not significant influence on their academic stress.

Keywords: Adjustment, B. Ed teacher trainees.

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Introduction: Education has a lot of responsibilities among which one major responsibility is to make a child not only human resource but human in real sense. Gandhiji has quoted education as a process of drawing the best from a child. But in formal settings this process is through study of various subjects, development of skills from the interaction in the class. In this relation teacher training plays a vital role. Simply learning and ignoring is not at all a matter

in the teaching profession because they can manage their profession in well respective manner and they will enter into shape the younger minds and really they will become the role models. Adjustment is nothing but the interaction between a person and environment. In other words, both personal and environmental factors work side by side in the adjustment process. Students spend a sizeable portion of their time in field work, which influences their total personality.

Review of related studies in the present study the investigator has reviewed the research done in the field of adjustment of B. Ed teacher trainees. Nidhi and Kermene (2015) **studied** that there was no significant difference found in adjustment problems of high academic achievement students and low academic achievement students. Jatindra Borah & Prof. Kaberi Saha (2018): finds that home adjustment of urban and rural B.Ed. teacher trainees were found to be more or less same as the differences of the Mean score of the two groups are not found significant. A. Anand & R. Annadurai, Ph. D (2012) focused that There is significant difference between men and women, married and unmarried, arts and science, rural and urban B.Ed., trainees in their adjustment pattern. There is a significant difference between married and unmarried B.Ed., trainees in their adjustment pattern Patel M. Darshanaben, Dixit S.P. (2013) conducted that there is no difference of adjustment problems of the girl trainees of above 25 and below 25 years of age.

Need for and importance of the study Education is the key component in national development in the end of globalization and technology the world is changing fast and continuously. To cope up with the demand of a changing world needs quality education. It may be 10th five-year plan or 11th year plan, one can see focus of enrolment has been shifted to quality education and quality of education depends upon the quality of the teachers. And to prepare future teachers is essential need, within years of professional courses they have heavy curricula such as 8 compulsory courses, 2 method courses, 1 special field, practice teaching phase, lots of assignment and academic work. It is difficult to complete the curriculum as suggested by Kothari and Shelat in the article of issue of teacher education (University News) 2 years B.Ed. course suggest, will provide most enough time for professional development. Due to 1 year B.Ed. course, there is a lot of stress on the students. They have all the programmes conducted 1 by 1 and along with this some students may have the problem of medium of instruction considered as academic problem.

To cope with such academic problems, there is the first need of psychological preparation of students, having aspiration to complete effectively and learning needs to understand how to be adjusted. This is possible only when they are healthy, socially & emotionally well-adjusted at

home. Education is also one of the basic factors. At the present time there is a lot of emphasis on IQ&EQ. However, one is intelligent if he/she is not stable emotionally will create problem.

Objectives of the Study

1. To assess the level of adjustment among B. Ed teacher trainees and to classify it.
2. To study the influence of the adjustment among B. Ed teacher trainees differ with respect to following variables.
 - Gender (Male/ Female)
 - Location (Urban/ Rural)
 - Marital status (Married/Unmarried)
 - Academic stream(science/Arts)

Hypotheses of the Study

In order to achieve the forecasting objectives, the following hypotheses were framed: 1. The following variables do not have a significant influence on the adjustment of teacher trainees.

- a) Gender (Boys/ Girls)
- b) Location (Urban/ Rural)
- c) Marital status (Married/Unmarried)
- d) Academic stream (science/Arts)

Definitions of the key terms: Adjustment: Adjustment is nothing but the interaction between a person and environment. In other words, both personal and environmental factors work side by side in the adjustment process.

Teacher trainees: Aspirants of would be a teacher in the future.

Population of the study: All the 300 Students studying in the Adikavi nannaya university of West Godavari district - during the academic year 2019-20 batch constituted the population of the study.

Sampling Size: The size of the proposed sample is stratified random sampling technique of 13 Teacher Education institutions and 300 B. Ed teacher trainees covering all the above-mentioned variables. It means each college will be randomly selected from 20-25 students on the day of administration of the tools.

Research Tool Used: Bell's adjustment inventory (Revised) : It is a standardized tool by Dr. R.K. OJHA. The tool to be used for assessing adjustment levels of B. Ed teacher trainees. This adjustment inventory includes four parts-Home, Health, Social and Emotional. Each part has 35 statements, which are answered in 'Yes' and 'No' For each 'Yes' responses 1 score is to be given. The total number of 'Yes' scores thus make total score of the individual in the part . The inventory is totally negative inventory. When an individual answers in 'Yes'. It indicates his difficulties. Therefore only 'Yes' responses scored to measure adjustment difficulties.

Reliability and validity of the tool: The adjustment inventory possesses high reliability. The reliability coefficients were determined by the Test-Retest method. The reliability coefficients are Home-0.91, Health-0.90, Social-0.89, Emotional-0.92. The adjustment inventory was validated against K. Kumar's Adjustment inventory.

Data analysis & Interpretation

OBJECTIVE: 1 To assess the level of adjustment among B. Ed teacher trainees and to classify it.

Table 5: Mean, % of Mean S.D. and $1/5^{\text{th}}$ of mean of total sample in adjustment of B. Ed teacher trainees.

<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>% of Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>$1/5^{\text{th}}$ of Mean</i>
300	68.22	22.74%	17.67	13.64

Interpretation: B. Ed teacher trainees are found to have average level of adjustment. Since $1/5^{\text{th}}$ of mean value is less than the S.D value, the sample of pupils is heterogeneous in adjustment. The sample shows variation in adjustment of teacher trainees.

Classification of B. Ed teacher trainees—basing on adjustment levels

On the basis of the mean adjustment score, the investigator would like to categorize the sample teacher trainees into three groups viz. Excellent adjustment, average adjustment and unsatisfactory adjustment. The following table shows the number of teacher trainees of these three categories:

Table 6: Distribution of Teacher trainees according to Adjustment category

S. No	Adjustment category	No of teacher trainees	Percentage
1	Unsatisfactory	56	18.6%
2	Average	209	69.6%
3	Excellent	35	11.6%

Interpretation: B. Ed teacher trainees are found to have average level on their adjustment. And the pictorial representation of this is presented as a pie chart given below.

GRAPH: 2 The given below pie diagram shows the levels of adjustment of B. Ed teacher trainees

OBJECTIVE: 4 To study the influence of the adjustment among B. Ed teacher trainees differ with respect to following variables.

- 1) Gender (Male/ Female)
- 2) Location (Urban/ Rural)
- 3) Marital status (Married/Unmarried)
- 4) Academic stream (science/Arts)

Table: 7 Table showing the variable wise distribution Mean, S.D., and *t* - value for the Adjustment of B. Ed teacher trainees.

<i>Sl. No</i>	<i>Variable</i>	<i>Type</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>S.D</i>	<i>t-value</i>	<i>Status of hypotheses</i>
1	Gender	Male	91	71.28	12.42	2.35**	Rejected
		Female	209	66.88	19.40		
2	Locality	Rural	139	68.84	16.79	0.57*	Accepted
		Urban	161	67.68	18.43		
3	Marital status	Married	134	69.25	16.07	0.92*	Accepted
		Unmarried	166	67.39	18.87		
4	Academic stream	Science	152	68.07	17.82	0.15*	Accepted
		Arts	148	68.37	17.57		

** Significant at 0.01 & 0.05 level. * Not significant at 0.05 level

Table values for 1.96 at 0.05 level and 2.58 at 0.01 level.

Discussion:

Students have to face many academic demands, because students are unable to adjust him in changing condition. There arise the need to be Social, Emotional, Educational, Health, home adjusted to make the student stress free and understand them very well need to know adjustment problem. To cope with such academic problems, there is the first need of psychological preparation of students, having aspiration to complete effectively and learning needs to understand how to be adjusted. This is possible only when they are healthy, socially & emotionally well adjusted.

Conclusion:

B. Ed teacher trainees are found to have average level on their adjustment. Another appreciable finding is that male teacher trainees are more adjusted than the female teacher trainees. Gender significantly influences their adjustment. Locality of living, marital status and academic stream has not significant influence on their adjustment. Another appreciable finding is that rural teacher trainees are on par with urban in their level of adjustment.

Therefore, efforts are to be made caring these directions to measure the academic stress in teacher education course by focusing more on concepts in developing adjustment pattern, positive attitude and exercise the developing the professional skills and real-life situations and re-orienting the teachers and parents towards these aspects.

Educational implications

The trainee students who feel more stress may be given special guidance and counselling. Girl students should need special attention in this aspect. Teacher educators should take special attention on those students who are unable to cope up with practical work.

Factors other than the training methods, curriculum etc may generate stress in prospective teachers which may adversely affect their attitude towards the course and they may not be fully benefited by the training. Hence trainee teachers are to be helped through stress coping mechanisms like meditation, yoga etc.

Lack of regularity in work especially in teacher training course is one of the causes for academic stress. This is to be focused while giving instructions to teacher training students.

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